

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH FOR GAINING COMPETITIVENESS ON THE MARKET OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

The environment or business environment has a significant impact on the development of economic activity. This is because every business organization operates under the conditions imposed by its environment. These conditions are determined by many factors, which can be divided into two groups, internal and external. Characteristic of these factors is that they are always dynamic.

The purpose of the article is to clarify the specifics of market structures for agricultural products and the possibilities for differentiating agricultural products.

Analyzing the market environment is a process of evaluating and integrating the collected information. Through it, the entrepreneur must be able to determine the upcoming changes, which in turn are the likely threats and opportunities for the company. All this helps the farmer to assess the market conditions at the moment and develop a marketing strategy for the future.

KEYWORDS: competitiveness, market power, agricultural products

ABSTRAKT

Die Umwelt oder das Unternehmensumfeld hat einen erheblichen Einfluss auf die Entwicklung der Wirtschaftstätigkeit. Das liegt daran, dass jedes Unternehmen unter den Bedingungen arbeitet, die ihm von seinem Umfeld auferlegt werden. Diese Bedingungen werden von vielen Faktoren bestimmt, die in zwei Gruppen unterteilt werden können: interne und externe. Charakteristisch für diese Faktoren ist, dass sie stets dynamisch sind.

Ziel des Artikels ist es, die Besonderheiten der Marktstrukturen für landwirtschaftliche Erzeugnisse und die Möglichkeiten zur Differenzierung landwirtschaftlicher Erzeugnisse zu klären.

Die Analyse des Marktumfelds ist ein Prozess der Auswertung und Integration der gesammelten Informationen. Dadurch muss der Unternehmer in der Lage sein, die bevorstehenden Veränderungen zu bestimmen, die wiederum die wahrscheinlichen Bedrohungen und Chancen für das Unternehmen darstellen. All dies hilft dem Landwirt, die gegenwärtigen Marktbedingungen zu beurteilen und eine Marketingstrategie für die Zukunft zu entwickeln.

Stichworte: Wettbewerbsfähigkeit, Marktmacht, landwirtschaftliche Erzeugnisse

RÉSUMÉ

L'environnement ou l'environnement des entreprises a un impact significatif sur le développement de l'activité économique. En effet, chaque entreprise fonctionne dans les conditions imposées par son environnement. Ces conditions sont déterminées par de nombreux facteurs, qui peuvent être divisés en deux groupes : les facteurs internes et les facteurs externes. La caractéristique de ces facteurs est qu'ils sont toujours dynamiques.

L'objectif de cet article est de clarifier les spécificités des structures du marché des produits agricoles et les possibilités de différenciation des produits agricoles.

L'analyse de l'environnement du marché est un processus d'évaluation et d'intégration des informations recueillies. Grâce à elle, l'entrepreneur doit être en mesure de déterminer les changements à venir, qui constituent à leur tour les menaces et les opportunités probables pour l'entreprise. Tout cela aide l'agriculteur à évaluer les conditions actuelles du marché et à élaborer une stratégie de marketing pour l'avenir.

MOTS-CLÉS: compétitivité, pouvoir de marché, produits agricoles

INTRODUCTION

The environment or business environment has a significant impact on the development of economic activity. This is because every business organization operates under the conditions imposed by its environment [Borisov and Radev, 2020]. These conditions are determined by many factors, which can be divided into two groups, internal and external [Borisov, 2021]. Characteristic of these factors is that they are always dynamic.

The purpose of the article is to clarify the specifics of market structures for agricultural products and the possibilities for differentiating agricultural products.

Analyzing the market environment is a process of evaluating and integrating the collected information. Through it, the entrepreneur must be able to determine the upcoming changes, which in turn are the likely threats and opportunities for the company. All this helps the farmer to assess the market conditions at the moment and develop a marketing strategy for the future [Borisov and Miladinovski, 2022].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The environment or business environment has a significant impact on the development of economic activity. This is because every business organization operates under the conditions imposed by its environment. These conditions are determined by many factors, which can be divided into two groups, internal and external. Characteristic of these factors is that they are always dynamic [Rezeal, Borisov, Radev, and Osmani, 2019]. Therefore, for business organizations, changes in the market environment create conditions for success, but also for uncertainty and threat. Despite the fact that the future is unpredictable, entrepreneurs estimate the likelihood of certain changes occurring. Farmers who fail to respond to changes in the market environment leave their business unprepared to deal with the changes that occur, which can lead to undesirable results [Radev, Borisov and Miladinovski, 2019]. Therefore, the monitoring of market subjects is of vital importance for the functioning of agricultural holdings and for the achievement of their long-term goals. To monitor changes in the market environment, entrepreneurs perform scanning and analysis [Borisov and Radev, 2020]. Scanning the market environment is the process of gathering information about the factors of that environment. It includes monitoring secondary sources such as: business, trade, government and other publications and marketing research. It is necessary to determine well what information they need, since not always a lot of information allows accurate conclusions to be drawn [Borisov and Garabedian, 2020]. Analyzing the market environment is a process of evaluating and integrating the collected information. Through it, the entrepreneur must be able to determine the upcoming changes, which in turn are the likely threats and opportunities for the company.

Two general approaches to responding to changes in the market environment are described in the literature [Borisov, Stoeva and Dirimanova (2021)]. One of them makes it possible to consider the

subjects of the market environment as completely uncontrollable and difficult to predict. In this approach, business organizations are passive towards the environment. In the second approach, they treat the environment aggressively and try to influence the entities determining the specifics of the market environment. Can't say which approach is better. The choice of one or the other is influenced and depends on the entrepreneur's philosophy, goals, financial capabilities, skills, etc. The task of the farmer is to study the market subjects in the most detail and, based on the results, make the right management decisions.

Internal factors. These are the factors that are amenable to management by the agricultural producer and are formed by the behavior of the personnel, the production processes, the finances of the agricultural holding. These factors are grouped into strengths and weaknesses. If an element has a positive impact on the company, it is considered a strength. If one factor hinders the company's development, it is a weakness. Internal factors determine how the organization progresses, both as an independent organizational unit and in response to the external environment.

The staff is an important factor with the help of which the set goals of the business organization are realized. It is obvious that the range of different qualifications to be taken into account in the selection of workers on a given farm can be very wide. This is because the activity in the production and sale of the product is, by its very nature, work with people and information. In this regard, the entrepreneur must monitor, report and exercise the motivation of his employees. The employees who join are very important. If managed properly, they can change the politics of the organization. However, poor staff management can lead to a disastrous situation for the company.

The production of a product requires the application of a certain technology. Technology is a set of methods and means to achieve a desired result; a way of converting the given into the necessary. Questions related to the used machines, equipment, tools, raw materials and materials are resolved here. Manufacturing is part of a complex process that depends on raw materials, human capital and labor, and the capacity to produce goods and services to meet people's needs according to demand. and their supply.

The finances of the agricultural holding ensure its activity and its opportunities for development. In this sense, financial resources are an important prerequisite for the successful implementation of the planned economic activities. That is why it is important that the finances of the agricultural holding are well managed.

External factors (microenvironment). These are market entities that have a direct relationship with agriculture - suppliers, intermediaries, competitors and customers. Every company functions under certain external conditions that make demands on its behavior. The consideration, consideration and adjustment of the company's activity to these conditions are essential for its further development. They have a significant impact on her chances of survival and her prospects, while she can hardly influence the nature of the changes in her. That is why it is very important for every company to study the emerging and forecast possible changes in the environment, to evaluate the favorable opportunities and threats that they bring to it. As a result, it can and should develop strategies for adapting to and changing these conditions. The company's environment is a set of all external forces, actions and conditions that affect its ability to fulfill contractual obligations, to improve its relations with consumers, as well as its opportunities for future development. These external factors, forces and conditions are the elements of the environment. On the layer side, it is composed of micro and macro environment.

The microenvironment consists of the firm's immediate surroundings that affect its ability to serve its markets.

Suppliers are companies, organizations or individual legal entities that supply the business organization with the necessary raw materials, materials and services. A marketing policy aimed at collecting the necessary information, comparison and selection of the offered prices, term of delivery and their quality, terms and methods of payments, additional services, etc. must be conducted with them. In this way, the individual firm has a selective attitude towards suppliers. Organizations get the resources they need through a network of suppliers. But some have one supplier and others have many. Therefore, they are to varying degrees dependent on the provider.

Suppliers pose a threat or source of stress to an industry primarily through the ability to raise prices or lower the quality of the goods and services they supply. Strong suppliers can "squeeze" profitability into a particular business if it is unable to cover its increased costs with price increases. The company must determine and analyze the number of its suppliers, motivate the reasons for using their services and production. It is necessary to highlight the advantages and disadvantages of the applied procurement and inventory management systems.

We distinguish several varieties of the supplier factor.

Material suppliers - the company is dependent on the quantity, quality, volume, price and delivery time.

Providers of financial resources - for a company to prosper, it needs not only materials, but also capital. Hence its dependence on government funding programs, banks, shareholders and private individuals.

Labor suppliers and labor market - without people capable of effectively using complex technology, materials and capital with a specific task, a firm cannot prosper. It needs highly qualified specialists.

Intermediaries are companies, organizations and legal entities that are mainly related to the realization of the product. Here it is necessary to note that the intermediaries realize the production of the producers and to some extent facilitate his activity. This requires special attention to management decisions related to the choice of sales channels and work with market intermediaries. Intermediaries are a traditional and widespread form of customer market access. Manufacturers need their services when entering a new market, when distributing a new product, as well as when it is necessary to optimize distribution costs. From the point of view of the criterion of ownership of the product they market, intermediary companies are divided into: commercial intermediaries, physical distributors,

Proprietary traders buy the manufacturer's products on the basis of a brokerage contract in order to sell them for their own profit. Very often these intermediaries act as wholesalers (distributors). Also, resellers can be retailers (dealers) who sell on their own behalf and at their expense the products purchased from the manufacturer or from the wholesaler to end users. The second large group of intermediaries, also called functional intermediaries, includes the variety of agents who do not acquire ownership of the products they offer or buy for their customers. These include commission agents, consignors, commercial representatives, brokers, factors and others.

Competitors are business entities that have oriented their activities towards the same customers. They offer similar products, therefore it is necessary to determine the main competitors and know their

potential (size, goals, financing) and marketing strategy (market share, product assortment, product quality, pricing strategies and other characteristics suitable for understanding their market behavior). In today's conditions, every manager should know that if he does not satisfy the needs of his buyers at least as much as they are satisfied by competitors, the organization will not stay afloat for long. Often, not only consumers but also competitors determine what to sell and at what price.

It is necessary to identify the main competitors of a company in the country and abroad, their goods and services, price policy and market share. Important questions are:

- Studying their market - what part of their activity is competitive with the company, what is their share of the market, how is it distributed geographically, what changes are expected over time, who are the users of their products and why
- The study of their production activity - capacities, plants, enterprises, divisions, sizes, location, flexible automated production systems, costs of raw materials, production costs, etc.
- Study of technological resources (patents, know-how) and human resources
- Study of competitors' marketing activity - system for studying the market, assortment, prices, service, distribution channels, advertising, employment.
- Financial status of competitors - own and borrowed funds, long-term and short-term investment, liquidity of funds, depreciation policy.

The customers are the ones who buy the products produced in the farms. In this regard, the farmer must study consumer behavior in order to win them over as regular buyers (customers). For this purpose, a system of user characteristics and indicators is used, through which the market is divided into parts. Knowing them facilitates the selection of the marketing policy and is especially important when making decisions about the marketing strategy. The goal is to find a good customer (buyer) who pays well and on time, expanding their own markets and appreciating the importance of the products offered.

Table 1. User research features and metrics. Source: [Dietel, 1992]

Characteristic of the separation on the market	User features	
	General	Specific
A. Objective	1. Demographic factors: /gender, age, profession, education, standard of living, place of residence/ 2. Socio-economic factors /volume of consumption, income, traditions, etc./	1. Method of consumption – often, occasionally in large quantities, in small quantities, in medium quantities 2. Loyalty to certain commodity signs - brand, stores, method of sale and purchase
B. Subjective	3. Characteristic personality traits 4. Lifestyle	3. Way of buying behavior - determination, indecision, neutrality, phlegmatic, etc. 4. Reaction of the marketing means – price, advertising, who makes the purchase decision and who implements it, etc.

External factors (macro environment). In the field of business, the study of the elements determining the external market environment (macro-environment) acquires special importance. They are the following: demographic, economic, natural and ecological, political, scientific and technical, legal, cultural and competition. The specified elements of the external market environment cannot be controlled by the business organization, but it must comply with them in order to successfully achieve its goals.

Demographic conditions need to be known, because the market consists primarily of people. The processes of fertility, mortality, aging, changing characteristics of the family are some of the most important factors directly related to the size of the market. Changing demographic conditions are having a major impact on demand. For example, an increase in the population of a country always leads to an increase in the demand for food products and everything related to their production. Their producers will always have a better chance of exporting there than in countries where the population is declining.

Market demographic analysis is very important because population is one of the main components of any market. Therefore, special attention should be paid to demographic characteristics.

The potential of the market in a given country is also determined by current incomes, production prices, the volume of savings, the possibilities of obtaining credits and others. Their parameters depend on the economic conditions and the created economic mechanism, which to a very large extent influence the so-called solvent demand. It also depends on the inflation rate, growth rates, unemployment, interest rates, etc. In this regard, economic conditions must be constantly analyzed in order to implement a correct marketing policy in business.

The main criterion for measuring the market potential is the reliability of the researched data, which should be checked with at least one additional source to confirm their legitimacy.

Some of the methods used to research market potential are:

- Statistical information
- Statistical studies of legitimate market research organizations
- Own market research of target audience by creating surveys and questionnaires
- SWOT
- How they position themselves in the market
- Competitive products and differences with them
- Problems that different products solve
- Customer benefits of different products
- Factors in customer decision making
- Key Selling Points

The most reliable method of measuring market potential is the official statistics, but with a comment that it must give reliable information, and this is possible only if correct source information is available, which is a component of these statistics.

The influence of natural and environmental factors has grown a lot in recent years. They are related to the climatic and geographical conditions, the distribution of natural resources and the production of ecologically clean products. Increasingly, these conditions are associated as part of human activities contributing to environmental pollution and damage to the human organism. Therefore, natural

and environmental issues occupy an increasingly important place in the study and analysis of the market environment.

Political conditions reflect political stability, ethnic and religious relations. A particularly important condition for companies involved in international business is the study of the international political situation. For a given country, the level of government, lifestyle, economic policy and capital are analyzed. Last but not least, the influence of social and professional groups, public organizations, science, etc. must also be taken into account. on political decision-making.

Studying the scientific and technical environment is an important prerequisite for the success of business organizations. It is necessary to analyze technological innovations and changes that have a huge impact, both on production processes and on the way of life and behavior of consumers and their preferences. Of particular importance are the legal regulations regulating the performance of the relevant activities in each country. In order to assess that there are prerequisites for actively entering a new market, the company and its marketers must thoroughly study the system of legal norms relating to the production, import and trade of the relevant goods in the given market.

In terms of understanding and knowing the external market environment, culture occupies a particularly important place. Broadly speaking, culture means traditions, mores, customs, religion, education, preferences, the way buying decisions are made, etc. Every country is characterised by some commonly accepted value system which influences the ways in which each individual behaves. It is a well-known fact that in order to gain a good position on the international market it is necessary to know the so-called potential customers in detail. In practice, business organisations and especially those in international business deploy their activities in a marketing environment full of competitors. One of the tasks of every business actor is to know, observe and try to outperform their competitors. This activity is directed towards the market in order to satisfy needs. It is known that anyone who serves the same needs appears as a competitor. In conclusion to the issues raised, it should be noted that the factors of the market environment should be studied, analysed and evaluated as favourable or otherwise. Moreover, these factors are always dynamic, which is why it is necessary to monitor changes and especially trends in their development. The main characteristic of a public environment is its composition. In a marketing sense, it is determined by various individuals and public groups who are interested in the economic activity of companies and can seriously influence their development. These are representatives of local and central government, banking circles, trade unions, associations, chambers of commerce, journalists, politicians, etc., who shape public opinion. In this regard, companies must conduct and maintain good contacts with the specified persons and public groups (Public relations). Through these contacts, companies strive to create a good image among the public. A specific place in the Public Relations system is occupied by the statements that companies also perform important public functions, influencing their future marketing positions.

Depending on the organization of the market, the behavior of the main market entities is predetermined. The behavior of the entrepreneur is determined depending on the number of companies that offer production on a given market, on the nature of the produced production, on the freedom of access to the market. Knowledge of market organization helps to explain the behavior of firms selling their products and to make predictions about reactions to changes in market conditions.

Several conditions must be present for a market to be defined as perfectly competitive. Conditions affect the behavior of each farm and the nature of the industry in which it operates.

In perfect competition, the producer has no control over price. It can raise or lower the rate of production and sales without having an effect on the cost of the output sold. The individual producer receives the market price of his output as a result of the general demand and supply of a uniform product. The competitive market is made up of a large number of producers who have a small share in the industry, therefore they cannot influence the market price.

Farmers produce uniform products. Therefore, there are perfect substitutes for buyers, so the producer must comply with the market price in order not to lose all his buyers. The demand curve for agricultural products is a horizontal line at the market price level, i.e. demand is perfectly elastic. The decisions made by the individual entrepreneur do not depend on the decisions of the other companies in the industry. Firms are related only through the given market price and therefore perfect competition is defined as price competition.

The industry can be entered and exited.

New entrepreneurs are attracted by the assumption that incumbent firms will make good profits. When a firm exits the industry it simply stops producing due to insufficient profits and due to incurred losses.

CONCLUSION

Market structure shows those characteristics of the market affecting the behavior of firms and determine the relationship between the market demand curve and the supply of the product of an individual firm.

Market organization reflects the way an industry is structured. By industry we understand the set of companies producing the same or uniform product.

The market organization, which is related to the structure of the agricultural sector, can be described by the following characteristics:

- many and relatively small farmers;
- the product is most often standard, with a low degree of differentiation;
- there is no ability of an individual farm to influence the price of production;
- free entry and exit from the market, as the free access of competitors determines the dynamic size of the industry.

The market structure of the agricultural sector is characterized by a high degree of competitiveness, which determines the weak influence of individual producers on the market. The structure of the market is more competitive and its influence on the behavior of each producer is often critical.

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